

PHILOSOPHY

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND HUMAN: RULES OF INTERACTION

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Abstract

Introduction. The article presents an analysis of philosophical and ethical issues that arise during the development, operation, and integration of artificial intelligence (AI) systems into human society and culture. The central issue is the morality of AI and human responsibility for its actions, as well as the need to establish new norms and protocols for interacting with this technology.

The purpose of the article is to justify the need to develop ethical codes for teams of AI developers and users, as well as protocols for the interaction of artificial intelligence with humans.

AI is not an ordinary technology, but a materialised representation of a human being's self-image. It lacks the free will, consciousness, and ontological stability necessary to make moral choices or actions. An ethical code for interaction with AI must anticipate technological advances and primarily define the behaviour and responsibilities of humans – developers and customers. The use of AI in illegal activities should be considered an aggravating circumstance.

Instead of attempting to teach machines empathy and technically implement moral principles, it is proposed that protocols be developed for AI interaction with humans. Protocols for AI must be thoroughly defined, considering the specific needs, safety, benefits, priorities, and individual needs of each person. They should include a diagnosis of the ethical issue, risk assessment, intervention conditions, solution options, and observation duration. The use of moral and ethical concepts when defining principles integrated into AI is not recommended.

Moral choice remains the exclusive prerogative and responsibility of humans. The role of AI is to model cognitive and emotional abilities, serving as a tool for self-knowledge and critical introspection of human nature and social phenomena. While AI is a research tool, its significant complexity suggests the need to consider the question of responsibility not only to humanity but also to artificial intelligence itself.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, code of ethics, responsibility, morality, human, technology.

Introduction. The issue of artificial intelligence (AI) safety and the development of ethical standards for working with it, intuitively understandable to non-experts, is of concern to both businesses and philosophers. To resolve this issue, it is necessary to clarify what we are dealing with: a sentient being or a technical system simulating cognitive processes. On the other hand, the difficulty of creating general AI stems not only from technical limitations and an insufficient understanding of the human mind, but also from the uncertainty of the developers' own goals: do they want to create an obedient agent, a highly specialised device, or a universal intelligent being, fully human-like?

It is impossible to stop the development of artificial intelligence, but concerns about its negative consequences are growing. Developers and users fear losing control over AI, which hinders productive work. Embedding ethical principles in programs that regulate AI behaviour, especially in relation to humans, is becoming the last line of defence. Instead of relying on the moral principles of developers and users, some researchers (Voeneky S. et al., 2022, p. 2) propose implementing “artificial morality” in AI.

A shortcoming of existing AI ethical codes (Ethics of AI..., 2023; Ramos G., 2023; Principles of Ethical Use..., 2022; What is AI Ethics?, 2025) is that they contain general provisions in the style of “do no harm”. For most people engaged in social interactions within a

particular culture, these provisions seem intuitively understandable. However, when dealing with a new technology, unprecedented in the history of human civilization, a more detailed explanation of each point of the ethical code is required, as well as a clear distinction between what from the established list of provisions is the prerogative of humans, what is prescribed for AI, what can be left to the discretion of algorithms, and what must be controlled by humans.

The purpose of this article is to justify the need to develop ethical codes for teams of AI developers and users, as well as protocols for interaction between artificial intelligence and humans.

The main materials. Key qualities of intelligence are the ability to learn, adapt to changing conditions, and act in accordance with community-established norms. It is naive to expect artificial intelligence to adhere to safety measures and ethical principles if the people involved in its development and use engage in immoral behaviour. This applies both to general AI, which is capable of independent decision-making but is still in development (Swan et al., 2022, p. 1), and to already developed types of AI, since their programming and use are carried out by individuals, each of whom has their own system of moral values by which they act.

Recent research shows that it is impossible to create an “ideologically impartial” artificial intelligence (Buyl M. et al., 2025). Ideological principles and ethical judgments are inextricably linked to the data used

to train AI, shaping its behaviour. Large language models (a type of artificial intelligence) continuously reproduce the judgment and value systems of a particular group of people. It embodies the experience and views of its creators – a small circle of specialists or those who financed its development – and inherits not only their knowledge but also certain worldview principles that hinder unbiased knowledge.

The creation of intelligent systems capable of rapid learning and improvement requires the development of an ethical code for interaction with AI. It is advisable to apply legal norms that define the degree of liability of individuals or legal entities for illegal actions, where the use of AI is considered an aggravating circumstance and can be interpreted as the involvement of a computing entity in criminal activity that is incapable of refusing to perform immoral or illegal actions. Using the work of developers for criminal purposes damages their business reputation and causes moral harm. Consumers should also bear responsibility for the consequences of using a product equally with the developer, both to society and to the AI itself. The development of legal and ethical norms must be ahead of technological advances, given the complexity and rapid evolution of artificial intelligence systems.

The unique feature of AI technologies is that the boundary between human nature and technological devices is even more blurred than with other types of technology. Artificial intelligence is the realisation of an understanding of human nature. However, AI will not replace humans; it operates on different principles than human intelligence, so different criteria are needed to determine interactions between AI and humans than those between people.

Ethical principles and codes created to regulate interpersonal relationships and interactions within teams are unsuitable for managing relationships with artificial intelligence systems and robotics. On the one hand, AI is a complex system that simulates cognitive functions, and its capabilities are rapidly evolving. On the other hand, it lacks autonomy in decision-making. Numerous calculations determine its functioning; it lacks free will, meaning it is incapable of deliberate action.

It now seems clear that AI will never be truly autonomous, that humans will not allow it to make decisions regarding their well-being, freedom, and future. However, this situation could change if AI systems significantly outnumber working humans or are delegated the majority of social and economic issues, as well as legal and educational matters. As artificial intelligence becomes an integral part of not only technology but also culture and social interactions, it must be equipped with the ability to make decisions under human supervision. AI is capable of learning and requires experience to determine the optimal interactions with humans. Therefore, in addition to ethical codes for humans, it is necessary to develop protocols for AI interaction with humans, based on its specifications and purpose.

The authors of the monograph (Voeneky S. et al., 2022) highlight the complexity of implementing moral principles technically, noting that the current stage of AI development renders it impossible to implement universal methods for embodying moral principles.

«An autonomous vehicle will demand a different approach to moral implementation than a domestic care robot». (Misselhorn C., 2022, p. 41).

Both programmers and philosophers agree that AI is fundamentally different from humans. However, scientists continue to attempt to develop human-like “feelings” and the capacity for empathy in machines. A paper (Christov-Moor L. et al., 2023) analyses attempts to incorporate empathy into AI and concludes that neither decoding human cognitive and affective states nor AI's ability to predict a person's internal state based on observed data leads to the development of empathy or promotes “prosocial decision-making”. The authors propose modelling such emotions and experiences computationally, as well as imparting to AI the existential experience of vulnerability, suffering, and the instability of the world.

Artificial intelligence is a technical device that possesses cognitive and intellectual skills, the ability to learn and develop, but is not comparable to a human personality. AI is ontologically unstable, lacking the autonomy necessary for moral judgment and ethical action. A distinctive feature of AI is that it acts in accordance with the task assigned to it, according to a given program, and based on circumstances. Its actions have no self-subsistent meaning (Durt C., 2022, p. 68). They are merely a series of events in a process of contextually determined randomness.

The authors of the monograph “Kant and Artificial Intelligence” rightly argue that AI is incapable of moral choice (Benossi & Bernecker, 2022). Morality is based not only on altruism and empathy, but also on an understanding of the significance of universal human values. Recognising morally valuable factors requires not only understanding but also experience of human relationships, as well as knowledge of universal human moral principles. This level of understanding is not available to every human being. AI is unlikely to achieve it in the foreseeable future.

The concepts of intelligence, rationality, consciousness, and others, as applied to technology and engineering, are metaphors and extrapolations of research findings on human cognitive abilities in the field of technology. Humans develop computations that simulate emotions and thought processes and interpret them as conscious (meaningful). Humans interpret the actions of algorithms as intelligent because the program's actions are feasible and logical.

The more deeply AI systems penetrate culture and social interactions, the greater their influence on society and the more frequently they face the need to make moral choices when making decisions regarding human well-being. Unlike humans, AI does not possess free will, as its decisions are based on algorithms and programs. The difficulty in creating moral AI is that applying ethical principles requires awareness of the moral choice situation. Therefore, in relation to AI, we are not discussing morality, but rather modelling ethical principles using technical means under specific conditions and learning under human supervision.

The impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on humans is complex. On the one hand, AI reveals weaknesses in human nature, making people more susceptible to vulnerabilities. Innovations in this field can open the door to manipulation, as they expose the limitations

of human capabilities. On the other hand, awareness of one's own weaknesses and problems motivates people to address them to avoid negative consequences, such as loss of employment or social status. This requires lifestyle adjustments and the development of new ways of interacting with AI. It is essential to recognise that AI is a distinct type of technology, and anthropomorphising it, as well as equating it with other types of technology, is unacceptable. People have not yet developed ways of socially interacting with AI (Brooks B., 2024). Specific methods for describing and interacting with AI must be developed that differ from the ways of interacting with people and other types of technology.

Conclusion. Not only should artificial intelligence have limitations on its actions to prevent harm to humans, but humans, for example, when instructing artificial intelligence to commit a crime, should also bear responsibility for it. AI is a tool, but one so complex that it makes sense to consider responsibility not only to humanity but also to the AI itself.

The concepts of morality and ethics should not be used to describe principles integrated into AI. It is more appropriate to develop protocols for interaction with people, similar to treatment protocols in medicine, which consistently and thoroughly prescribe the sequence of actions and as many variations as possible. These protocols should take into account the safety, benefits, priorities, and individual needs of people. They should contain general ethical provisions; a definition of the ethical rule to be applied; methods for identifying (diagnosing) a moral problem, assessing the risk of complications or negative consequences in the event of ignoring the problem or its improper resolution; conditions under which the AI assumes responsibility for solving the problem (intervenes); options for solving the problem, a set duration for monitoring the consequences of actions taken and, if necessary, behavioral adjustments; conditions for continuing the search for a solution to the moral problem or terminating the intervention.

Humanity constantly accumulates and loses knowledge and skills, some of which become obsolete over time. The loss of morality is tantamount to the loss of human essence. Delegating some decisions to artificial intelligence does not absolve one of responsibility and ethical principles – only the scope of their application changes. Moral choice is a human choice and a human responsibility. However, if AI ever achieves a level of consciousness sufficient to make ethical decisions, its development in this area should not be hindered. At the same time, situations involving human life and well-being where AI is forced to make decisions should be avoided.

AI is a masterpiece of human thought and a new stage in knowledge, but how it will be used and how its potential will be realised depends entirely on humans, even if its intellectual capabilities surpass those of humans. The intellectual superiority of artificial intelligence will either open up new space for the development of human capabilities or destroy humanity. In this respect, it is similar to most technological or cultural innovations, the thoughtless exploitation of which is destructive to both society as a whole and the individual.

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